

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CHAM****FIRST NAME: BAI****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the list below are the recommended citations for this Coursepack (using Turabian style- Author-Date Style and Reference List)?

- Author-Date Style and Reference List In-Text: (EUCLID 2024, page no.) or (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, page no.). Reference List: Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. Notes-Bibliography Style Footnote: Bibliography: Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack. Period 1.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *How to Write a Response Paper* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 2.

- Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.
- Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2024). Reference List: Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024.
- ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

2. What is Plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is using information that is not yours.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and acknowledges the author.
- Plagiarism includes taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Examples of plagiarism include taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you, put your name on it, and give it to your professor would be plagiarism.²**

3. What is research?

- Research means questioning others on issues one needs to understand.

² Ibid., 34.

- Research means inquiry to answer types of questions from others.
 - Research means a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but also others want to solve. Research thus includes the steps involved in presenting or reporting it³.**
 - Research is an inquiry to solve a problem that not only the researcher but also others want to solve. Research thus includes the steps involved in presenting or reporting it.
4. What is the distinction between pure and applied Research?
- Research is pure when it addresses a conceptual problem with no direct practical consequences and when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers. We call research applied when it addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.⁴**
 - Research is pure when it has no direct practical consequences and when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers. We call research applied when it addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.
 - Research is pure when that conceptual problem has direct practical consequences when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press 2018), 19.

⁴ Ibid., 30.

- Research is called applied when it addresses a problem that has practical consequences.

5. What are the different kinds of sources?

- There are different kinds of sources, and only two are mainly used, including primary and secondary research.
- Sources are categorized into many kinds: books, Newspapers, internet, and social media.
- Sources are conventionally categorized into three kinds: primary, secondary, and tertiary (think first-, second, and thirdhand). Their boundaries are fuzzy, but knowing these categories can help you conduct your research.⁵**
- Sources can be from anywhere and have no boundaries.

6. Explain the Difference between the types of sources a researcher uses.

- Primary sources are “original” materials that provide you with the “raw” data or evidence you will use to develop, test, and ultimately justify your hypothesis or claim, and Secondary sources are books, articles, papers, or reports that are based on primary sources and intended for scholarly or professional audiences. In contrast, Tertiary sources are books and articles that synthesize secondary sources for general readers. They include textbooks,**

⁵ Ibid., 35.

encyclopedias (including Wikipedia), dictionaries, and articles in publications for broad audiences, like Time and the Atlantic.⁶

- Tertiary sources are “original” materials that provide you with the “raw” data or evidence you will use to develop, test, and ultimately justify your hypothesis or claim, and Secondary sources are books, articles, papers, or reports that are based on primary sources and intended for scholarly or professional audiences. In contrast, Tertiary sources are books and articles that synthesize secondary sources for general readers. They include textbooks, encyclopedias (including Wikipedia), dictionaries, and articles in publications for broad audiences, like Time and the Atlantic.
 - Only Secondary sources are books, articles, papers, or reports based on primary sources intended for scholarly or professional audiences.
 - Tertiary sources are books and articles that synthesize secondary sources for general readers and are more important in research than primary sources.
7. What is a research argument, and what is not?
- It is a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues. As such, readers will not necessarily oppose your claims (although they might). However, they also will not accept them until they see good**

⁶ Ibid.

reasons based on reliable evidence and until you respond to their questions and reservations.⁷

- It evokes images of people shouting at one another.
- It is an argument to win, bludgeon, or intimidate one's opponent into assent or silence.
- You cooperate with your listeners by making an argument in a face-to-face conversation.

8. What is Quantitative and Qualitative Research?

- Quantitative research is suited to promoting a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants, whereas qualitative research is applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena. Both research approaches involve complex processes in which data-collection and data-analysis methods assume meaning and significance about the assumptions underlying the larger intellectual traditions within which these methods are applied.
- Qualitative research describes current conditions, investigates relationships, and studies cause-effect phenomena and understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants, whereas quantitative research is applied.

⁷ Ibid., 56.

Both research approaches involve simple processes in which data collection and analysis methods assume meaning and significance about the assumptions underlying the larger intellectual traditions within which these methods are applied.

Qualitative research is suited to promoting a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants. In contrast, quantitative is applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena. Both research approaches involve complex processes in which data collection and data analysis methods assume meaning and significance about the assumptions underlying the larger intellectual traditions within which these methods are applied.⁸

9. What are the main prerequisites and conditions for applying the World Health Organization reference and bibliography?

WHO information products must fulfill the ethical and legal requirements to acknowledge the sources of the information and opinions they give. They should provide readers with accurate and consistent links to additional, reputable, and formally published information on a topic. (This excludes drafts, presentations, and abstracts.) This acknowledgment can take two forms: references or a bibliography”.⁹

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications 2008), 34.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. Second edition (World Health Organization, 2013), 42.

- WHO information products must fulfill the legal requirements to acknowledge the sources of the information and opinions they give. They should provide readers with accurate and consistent links to additional, reputable, and formally published information on a topic. (This excludes drafts, presentations, and abstracts).
- This acknowledgment can take many forms.
- WHO information products need not fulfill the ethical and legal requirements to acknowledge the sources of the information and opinions they give. They should provide readers with accurate and consistent links to additional, reputable, and formally published information on a topic. (This excludes drafts, presentations, and abstracts).

10. What is your understanding of this statement below?

- I Agree that WHO is committed to working towards equality between all people, so its information products must reflect and pursue that commitment. WHO must address all people equally and fairly; it must not discriminate against, stereotype, or demean people based on their age, physical or intellectual impairments, ethnicity, sex, or sexual orientation. Stereotypes, for example, are broad generalizations that are applied to a person or group of people and detract from their individuality. In addition, WHO's main aim in publishing is to inform and persuade; both tasks are easier if WHO information products address users courteously and fairly".¹⁰**

¹⁰ Ibid., 61.

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- I disagree that WHO is not committed to working towards equality between all people, so its information products cannot reflect and pursue that commitment. WHO must address all people equally and fairly; it must not discriminate against, stereotype, or demean people based on their age, physical or intellectual impairments, ethnicity, sex, or sexual orientation. Stereotypes, for example, are broad generalizations that are applied to a person or group of people and detract from their individuality. In addition, the main aim of publishing is to inform and persuade; both tasks are easier if WHO information products address users courteously and fairly.
- I am not sure that WHO is committed to working towards equality between all people, so its information products cannot reflect and pursue that commitment. WHO must address all people equally and fairly; it must not discriminate against, stereotype, or demean people based on their age, physical or intellectual impairments, ethnicity, sex, or sexual orientation. Stereotypes, for example, are broad generalizations that are applied to a person or group of people and detract from their individuality. In addition, the main aim of publishing is to inform and persuade; both tasks are easier if WHO information products address users courteously and fairly.
- It is not true that WHO is not committed to working towards equality between all people, so its information products cannot reflect and pursue that commitment. WHO must address all people equally and fairly; it must not discriminate against, stereotype, or demean people based on their age, physical or intellectual impairments, ethnicity, sex, or sexual orientation. Stereotypes, for example, are

broad generalizations that are applied to a person or group of people and detract from their individuality. In addition, the main aim of publishing is to inform and persuade; both tasks are easier if WHO information products address users courteously and fairly.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.